

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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WEIGHT GAIN PATTERNS ASSOCIATED WITH VAGINAL BIRTH AFTER
CESAREAN: A STUDY PROPOSAL

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Women in the United States desirous of vaginal birth after cesarean (VBAC) have a 60%-80% chance of success. Inability to achieve VBAC may be related to various factors. One such factor, excessive gestational weight gain (GWG), has not been substantively addressed since the 2009 modification of the Institute of Medicine guideline. This retrospective case control study plan addressed the general question: To what extent does GWG predict VBAC? It also will address the more specific question: Do patterns of GWG predict VBAC? Following human subjects review, the proposed study will analyze data from women who attempted a trial of labor managed by a hospital based Nurse-Midwifery service with a 78% VBAC success rate. The hypothesis that there is a relationship between excessive GWG and decreased rate of VBAC will be tested using logistic regression. The sample will be described in terms of age and race/ethnicity, along with maternal and pregnancy conditions (e.g., comorbidities, history). Analysis will determine whether achievement of VBAC (yes/no) is related to GWG. This inquiry may highlight the importance of prenatal education to patients related to optimal weight gain in woman planning to attempt a trial of labor hoping to achieve VBAC. The results should identify needs for future research and information for targeting better education, treatment, and strategy to provide a safe, evidence-based environment for these women prior to, and during pregnancy.

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BACKGROUND

Needs Assessment/Problem Statement

In the United States, approximately one of every three women will undergo a cesarean delivery (Martin, Hamilton, Osterman, Curtin & Mathews, 2013; Marshall & Guise, 2011). This results in a significant population of women who during subsequent pregnancies face the decision of whether or not to attempt a vaginal birth. The National Institutes of Health (NIH) and American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG) recommend that a trial of labor should be offered after proper counsel to women who are appropriate candidates. In general, in absence of other prior uterine surgery or separate contraindications to vaginal delivery, a woman with a history of only one cesarean delivery and a low transverse scar is a candidate for vaginal delivery after cesarean (VBAC) (ACOG, 2010; NIH, 2010). This recommendation stems from the rationale that overall risk of morbidity and mortality is greater for a repeat cesarean delivery than a VBAC, and that risk of uterine rupture during a trial of labor is low. Short-term risks of cesarean delivery include increased mortality, risk for deep vein thrombosis, increased hospitalization time, and increased adverse events inherent to major abdominal surgery including but not limited to adhesions, infection, and trauma to bowel and bladder. Long-term risks include abnormal placenta implantation and/or growth through the uterine muscle resulting in a placenta accreta, increta, or percreta (Caughey, Cahill, & Rouse, 2014; Marshall & Guise, 2011; NIH, 2010).

Apart from the primary concern of short and long term risks of repeat cesarean delivery are cost implications. In the United States, the costliest category for private and public insurance entities is care during pregnancy. In 2004, a vaginal delivery charge averaged \$7,772 compared with that of \$12,223 for cesarean delivery. By 2009, the

average vaginal delivery charge was \$9,617 compared to \$15,779 for a cesarean delivery (Kozhimannil, Shippe, Adegoke, & Virnig, 2013).

Despite the World Health Organization (WHO) recommendation that cesarean delivery rates should be no higher than 15% (Chalmers, 1992), and respected professional obstetric organizations call for a decrease in the current rate (Caughey et al., 2014) cesarean delivery statistics continue to hold steady. Cesarean delivery rates dropped significantly (approximately 60%) between 1996 and 2009, then increased through 2010 and have stayed steady and unchanged (Martin et al., 2013).

In California, the primary cesarean delivery rate (women who deliver by cesarean for the first time), was approximately 20% in 2012 as published by the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services (Osterman & Martin, 2014). In Orange County California, hospital cesarean delivery rates including primary and repeat vary from 11-40%, with an average of 33% (Ramos, Nafday, Condon, Thiessen, & Bowen, 2011). Hospitals have been encouraged by professional organizations and insurers to explain and to lower these rates when possible. This is partly fueled recommendations of national professional organizations, the federal government support and instituting public data reporting, and public interest groups educating the general public about this data. One such example is found on www.CesareanRates.com (2014) where public data is compiled, listed, and organized in lay terms such as listing hospital statistics like South Miami Hospital's 61.9% cesarean delivery rate (Caughey, et al., 2014; NIH, 2010; Osterman & Martin, 2014; Ramos et al., 2011; Stanley, 2011).

Since the early 1900s, United States professional obstetric organizations have expressed varying opinions on the safety and practice of VBAC. As low transverse

incisions became more commonly used than classical vertical incisions during cesarean delivery, a much safer environment for trial of labor after cesarean evolved. In the 1950s and 1960s, evidence evolved that supported the relative safety of a trial of labor. Despite this, the cesarean delivery rate skyrocketed from 5.5% (1970) to 16.5% in 1980 and to 27.6% by 2003 (American Academy of Family Physicians, 2005). Current rates for cesarean delivery are even higher as previously discussed, hovering around 30% (Marshall & Guise, 2011; Martin et al., 2013; NIH, 2010).

In light of the increasing numbers of cesarean deliveries nationwide, adequate data supports the safety of trial of labor in low risk women. Following a comprehensive review of available data, members of a 2010 NIH consensus meeting and ACOG concluded that there is good, consistent evidence that trial of labor can be recommended for most women with a history of only one previous cesarean delivery (ACOG, 2010; Guise et al., 2010; NIH, 2010). Overall, there is a 60%-80% chance of achieving a VBAC when looking at the general population of women who attempt a trial of labor. However, certain risk factors decrease this chance. Risk factors with moderate to strong evidence according to the evidence report and technology assessment by Guise et al. (2010) include race and ethnicity (Hispanics, African Americans), increasing maternal age, single marital status, less than 12 years of education, delivery at rural and private hospitals, presence of maternal disease (e.g., hypertension, diabetes, asthma, seizures, renal disease, thyroid disease, heart disease), macrocosmic infant with primary cesarean delivery, gestational age greater than 20 weeks, and labor induction or augmentation. In addition to these risk factors, obesity and excessive weight gain are associated with greater risk of primary cesarean delivery as well (ACOG, 2010; Guise et al., 2010;

Juhasz, Gyamfi, Tocce, & Stone, 2005; Kominiarek et. al, 2010; Langford, Joshu, Chang, Myles, & Lect, 2011).

Research has historically illustrated various negative outcomes associated with excessive gestational weight gain (GWG), one of which is an increased risk factor for cesarean delivery as illustrated in Appendix 1. Weight gain in pregnancy is a complex physiological process in which the three components: the mother (extracellular fluid, protein, water, minerals, blood, fat tissue, breast tissue, uterus, and amniotic fluid), placenta, and fetus are thought to influence each other affecting GWG. It is recognized that these factors influence each other in both obvious and discrete ways not fully understood (Hyttén, 1991; Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009).

Rasmussen and Yaktine (2009) also illustrated that there is an expected variation in weight gain across ethnicities, age, and stature necessitating a range for appropriate weight gain rather than a single amount. In 2009, the Institute of Medicine (IOM) as authored by Rasmussen and Yaktine, published revised evidence syntheses and recommended pregnancy weight gain guidelines. Particularly, these included lower body mass index thresholds for women in all categories consistent with World Health Organization categories including a comparatively limited recommended GWG range for women who are obese.

Whereas in the past special populations of women such as women of short stature, pregnant adolescents, and racial or ethnic groups were hypothesized to gain weight differently, the IOM committee concluded that there is not sufficient evidence to recommend modification of guideline ranges of weight gain in these contexts. It was concluded that the World Health Organization ranges for GWG are applicable for all

special populations (Rasmussen et al., 2009). These recommendations are presented in Table 1.

Earlier guidelines (IOM, 1990) responded to concerns about preterm delivery and small-for-gestational-age infants whereas 2009 guidelines gave greater focus to the relationships among obesity, weight gain, and pregnancy and delivery outcomes.

Evidence regarding adverse outcomes in pregnancy related to excessive weight gain, and concerns by professional organizations over the IOM using body mass index categories dissimilar to those of the World Health Organization in part prompted the reexamination of weight gain in pregnancy and revised IOM guidelines (Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009).

Table 1

2009 IOM Recommendation For Total and Rate of Gestational Weight Gain

Prepregnancy BMI	Total Weight Gain		Rates of Weight Gain 2nd and 3rd Trimester	
	Range in kg	Range in lb	Mean (Range) in kg/wk	Mean (Range) in lb/wk
Underweight (< 18.5 kg/m ²)	12.5-18.0	28.0-40.0	0.51 (0.44-0.58)	1.0 (1.0-1.3)
Normal Weight (18.5-24.9 kg/m ²)	11.5-16.0	25.0-35.0	0.42 (0.35-0.50)	1.0 (0.8-1.0)
Overweight (25.0-29.9 kg/m ²)	7.0-11.5	15.0-25.0	0.28 (0.23-0.33)	0.6 (0.5-0.7)
Obese (> 30.0 kg/m ²)	5.0-9.0	11.0-20.0	0.22 (0.17-0.27)	0.5 (0.4-0.6)

Note. Calculations include 0.5-2 kg (1.1-1.4 lbs) weight in the first trimester (Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009).

Approximately 30-40% of women gain excessively during pregnancy (Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009). The fact that excessive gestational weight gain is prevalent and is a potentially modifiable risk factor for decreased success of a VBAC makes the topic of interest to providers in the United States. As discussed, excessive GWG is linked to increased morbidity and mortality in pregnancy, including increased risk for an indicated primary cesarean delivery (American College of Nurse-Midwives, 2011; Juhasz, et al., 2005; NIH, 2010). This increased risk may be translated to risk of trial of labor failure necessitating repeat cesarean delivery. However, current research on this is limited. Most

available evidence is related to excessive weight gain in women without history of cesarean delivery, or was reported prior the 2009 IOM weight gain in pregnancy guidelines (Bujold, Hammoud, Schild, Krapp, & Baumann, 2005; Hibbard et al., 2006; Juhasz et al., 2005; Kominiarek et. al, 2010; Langford, 2011, 2011; NIH, 2010; Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009).

In addition to excessive GWG overall, the pattern of gain may be influential in the achievement of VBAC. When illustrated by graphing weeks in pregnancy and GWG, the resulting curve for most women is sigmoid in shape. A general pattern of gain (within a range) is illustrated as constant for all women (Hyttén, 1991; Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009). The first trimester presents a time of minimal weight gain, approximately 1.1-1.4 lb, and then the second and third trimesters should demonstrate a gain of 0.4-1.3 lb per week according to the woman's pre-pregnancy BMI category (Table 1). It is recognized that this is an aggregate result of the various components that make up GWG. GWG is compositely due to approximately 1/3 weight from the fetus, placenta, and amniotic fluid and the other 2/3 mass from maternal components of the extracellular fluid, and fat, breast, uterus, and blood with an increase in plasma volume of 50% by 30-34 weeks (Hyttén, 1991; Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009). Current guidelines do not address the influence that excessive weight gain in a particular segment of gestation may have on outcomes of pregnancy and delivery including a trial of labor.

At Kaiser Permanente Orange County (KPOC), the Nurse-Midwifery service performs the majority of vaginal deliveries at its two hospitals and co-manages certain moderate risk patients with the Physician service. Since the advent of the Nurse-Midwifery service in 1980, over 65,000 vaginal deliveries have been performed by

Kaiser nurse-midwives. In 2012, the Nurse-Midwifery service primary cesarean delivery rate (low/medium risk patients) was 12.5%, a primary cesarean delivery rate below the WHO benchmark of 15% (Chalmers, 1992). Since 1997, over 2,000 women attempting a trial of labor have been managed by the Nurse-Midwifery service, with an average success rate of 78% achieving VBAC. This is at the high end of rates described in the literature (ACOG, 2010), and may reflect a best practice. It is unknown if this success rate is in part related to overall and/or specific patterns of appropriate weight gain (per 2009 IOM standards) during pregnancy.

Data available through KPOC provide an opportunity to learn about these relationships. This planned case control study aims to address the following question: To what extent does GWG (by itself or along with other variables) predict VBAC in women who attempt a trial of labor who have never before delivered vaginally? It also will address the more specific question: Do *patterns* of GWG predict VBAC in women who have never delivered vaginally? Weight gain appropriateness will be evaluated using the IOM 2009 BMI based categories (Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009). Learning from data archived by a Nurse-Midwifery practice with high rates of patients who achieve a successful vaginal birth after cesarean is a unique opportunity.

Supporting Framework

Figure 1 shows the study framework that guided the literature search and study design assisting in the determination of the population of interest, and what questions should be investigated. The population being studied is pregnant women with history of a primary cesarean delivery who desired VBAC and who delivered at KPOC under care of the Nurse-Midwifery service. There are three possible delivery outcomes: VBAC, an indicated repeat cesarean delivery (IRCD), or an elective repeat cesarean delivery

(ERCD). Women may require an indicated repeat cesarean delivery because of medical factors prior to labor, or factors discovered during a trial of labor. Thus, for this study the cases will be women who successfully achieve VBAC, and the controls will be women who deliver by an indicated cesarean delivery after a trial of labor. Women who elect a repeat cesarean delivery will not be studied.

Research Questions

Question 1: What is the association between patterns of GWG and VBAC in women with history of one cesarean delivery and without history of vaginal delivery?

Question 2: In women with history of one cesarean delivery and without history of vaginal delivery who attempt a trial of labor, to what extent does GWG predict VBAC given maternal/pregnancy-related factors that relate to VBAC (confounding variables)?

Weight gain will be operationalized in context of the BMI-based 2009 IOM guidelines (Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009):

1. Overall total gestational weight gain
2. Weight gain during the second and third trimesters

Overall total gestational weight gain, second trimester weight gain, and third trimester weight gain will be analyzed as well as for association with other variables (Appendix C). Figure 2 Infographic illustrates possible GWG patterns.

Figure 1. Supporting Model. PCD = history of primary cesarean delivery; 2ND/ 3RD = weight gain in the second, third trimesters; TOLAC = trial of labor after cesarean; VBAC = vaginal birth after cesarean; IRCD = indicated repeat cesarean delivery; ERCD = elective repeat cesarean delivery.

Figure 2. Infographic: seven categories of gestational weight gain patterns. Grey fill = appropriate gestational weight gain. Black fill = excessive gestational weight gain.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A literature search was performed to understand the current body of knowledge about the relationship between weight gain and obesity in pregnancy and achievement of VBAC, as well as exclusion criteria for attempting a trial of labor. There is limited literature since the revised IOM 2009 guidelines regarding GWG and achieving VBAC. Studies found were predominately retrospective, and the majority used convenience samples. Study samples were more often from single sites and overall demonstrated limited demographic variation.

Existing knowledge on the relationship between weight gain and VBAC was sought, and study information was organized into tables in order to denote differences in design, variables and their operationalization, and findings (Appendix A). More studies were done evaluating weight gain in pregnancy and incidental findings of variables related to primary cesarean delivery (not VBAC), or investigation of the likelihood of overweight/obese pregnant women achieving VBAC rather than investigations of GWG (in/not in the context of obesity) and its relationship to VBAC. A single study addressed this relationship (Juhasz et al., 2005). Juhasz et al. found that excessive GWG (according to earlier 1990 IOM guidelines defined as > 40 pounds) significantly increased risk for repeat cesarean delivery after a trial of labor, Odds ratio 0.63, 95% confidence interval 0.42-0.97, $p = .034$.

There is also limited evidence using the revised 2009 IOM guidelines regarding GWG specific to the second and third pregnancy trimesters. Chmitorz, von Kries, Rassmussen, Nehrig, and Ensenauer (2012) found that excessive weight gain by the second trimester can be used to signal high risk of overall excessive GWG. In fact, in all

weight categories, researchers determined that the sensitivity to predict total excessive GWG on the basis of second trimester cutoffs was greater than 70%. These authors concluded that limiting weight gain to overall appropriate amounts may decrease the risks of excessive weight gain in pregnancy.

Obesity in pregnancy and its relation to increased risk of cesarean delivery was an important factor to review literature on for this study. Krukowski, Bursac, McGehee, & West (2013) found that being overweight or obese at the start of pregnancy was the strongest predictor of excessive weight gain in pregnancy. In studies with pregnant overweight/obese women and VBAC, many had small sample sizes and did not distinguish pregnancy outcomes by high pre-pregnancy BMI. Findings showed that together, overweight and obese women demonstrated a significantly higher trial of labor failure rate (27-44% in overweight/obese; 14%-29% in normal weight women) than did normal weight women (Chauhan et al., 2001; Durnwald, Ehrenberg, & Mercer, 2004; Goodall, Ahn, Chapa, & Hibbard, 2004; Hammoud, Schild, Krapp, & Baumann, 2005; Hibbard et al., 2006). No other study analyzed outcomes by appropriateness of GWG based upon the 2009 IOM guidelines.

Other factors associated with achieving a VBAC are provider counseling and practice philosophy. Provider counseling to women eligible for a trial of labor can be biased. While measuring such a bias would be difficult, it would be important to know the general philosophy or norms within a hospital or practice, to contemplate its effect on the rate of women attempting trial of labor. If a study does not document this variable in some way, then this confounding factor cannot be assessed (Bujold et al., 2005; Carroll, Megann, Cauhan, Klauser, & Morrison, 2003; Durnwald et al., 2004; Hibbard et al.,

2009; Homer, Kurincuk, Spark, Brocklehurst, & Knight, 2010; Juhasz et al., 2005). If practice philosophy is pessimistic regarding trial of labor, or if few women choose to attempt a VBAC, then this limits the “normality” of the sample studied and thus, decreases the generalizability of results. Randomized control trials with pregnant women are not appropriate due to ethical implications for this vulnerable population. Arguably, the next best thing would be studies that look at samples with high rates of trials of labor (implying supportive practice philosophy of VBAC by providers or high rate of women choosing a trial of labor) so that determinants for success of a trial of labor may be assessed in a population that more closely resembles all women with a history of a single cesarean delivery and are again pregnant. This offered support to this current study of women who attempted a trial of labor with the Southern California Kaiser Permanente Orange County Nurse-Midwifery Service, where success of a trial of labor is at benchmark levels and supported and recommended by the collaborative Nurse-Midwife and Physician service as a whole.

The concept that different patterns of weight gain may have a relationship to increased rates of achieving a VBAC was supported specifically by two articles. Chmitorz et al. (2012) found that based on the revised 2009 IOM GWG guidelines, women who gained weight excessively during the second trimester mostly continue excessive gain and concluded that women are thus easily identified who may end up gaining excessively overall. In addition, Magann et al. (2011) illustrated that women who gain excessively according to the revised 2009 IOM GWG guidelines by 28 weeks have a far more significant risk for a cesarean delivery. Both sets of researchers pointed out that if excessive weight gain by the end of the second trimester increases risk for cesarean

delivery, and women who gain excessively by the end of the second trimester without intervention continue to gain excessively, this identifies a population who: (a) are more easily identified early for risk, (b) are likely to continue to increase their risk, and (c) may benefit from intervention to slow weight gain mid-pregnancy to decrease risk of cesarean delivery. However, no studies were found that evaluated an intervention of limiting weight gain mid-pregnancy when noted to be excessive during the second trimester and relation to achieving a VBAC. This supported the need to investigate patterns of weight gain in pregnancy and their relation to VBAC.

Factors which increase risk to the mother and/or fetus significantly during a trial of labor, and thus exclude women from attempting a trial of labor, were identified (Appendix B) in order to determine study sample exclusion criteria. Induction of labor/absence of spontaneous labor, history of more than one cesarean delivery, and a uterine scar other than a low transverse scar were selected as exclusion criteria due to their increased risk during a trial of labor and are often viewed as necessitating an indicated repeat cesarean delivery. Findings support the fact that induction of labor carries a higher risk of uterine rupture and other birth complications. Use of misoprostol, a commonly used cervical ripening method, showed the greatest risk for uterine rupture in women attempting a trial of labor (Aslan, Unlu, Agar, & Ceylan, 2002; Delaney & Young, 2003). History of more than one cesarean delivery was also determined to be an exclusion criterion. In their systematic review and meta-analysis, Marshall, Fu, and Guise (2011) found that the incidence of morbidity is greater "in a dose-response fashion with each additional cesarean delivery" (p. 262.e6). Women with multiple cesarean deliveries showed at times a double risk for uterine rupture, and significant increased risk for

needing blood transfusions and other interventions (Asakura & Myers, 1995; Tahseen & Griffiths, 2009). A uterine scar other than a low transverse scar was also established as an exclusion criterion. There is a small increase in chance of uterine rupture with a low vertical scar as opposed to a low transverse uterine scar (Keiser & Baskett, 2002; Shipp et al., 1999). Study authors also recognized that data is difficult to gather on trial of labor in women with classical scars because of their limited use, and historically case reported high risk for uterine rupture during labor.

Women with history of a vaginal delivery were also excluded from this study. These women were excluded because of their history of a vaginal delivery which impressively increases the likelihood of achieving VBAC (NIH, 2010). This significant increase in possibility of achieving VBAC was thought to potentially overshadow, or confound, results focusing on the relationship of weight gain patterns in pregnancy and achieving VBAC.

METHODS

This study will use preexisting data to explore the relationship between GWG in pregnancy and VBAC. According to Polit and Beck (2012), quantitative research utilizes deductive reasoning and a systematic approach to arrive at conclusions. This systematic approach fits well with the goal of inferring a relationship of weight gain, (appropriate vs. excessive), and success of a vaginal birth after cesarean. Baseline data on women will be gathered and organized from a KPOC Nurse-Midwifery service logbook of women who desired and started a trial of labor between 2009 and 2013 (rationale: electronic medical records are available for these women); data regarding associated variables not available in the logbook will be gathered from patients' electronic medical records. The study variables are presented in Appendix C. Patients will be assigned code numbers on a master document saved on the computer in the locked Anaheim Kaiser Permanente Medical Center Nurse-Midwife call room, under the primary researcher's user name log-on profile locked at all times when not in use by a personal code only known to the primary researcher. All de-identified data will be recorded on a separate electronic data collection form for each patient (see Appendix D for copy of this sheet). Data will be kept on a laptop owned by the primary researcher, locked at all times when not in use by a personal code only known to the primary researcher. A back up file will be shared with the Project Chair.

A substantial body of evidence supports the negative effect of excessive weight gain in pregnancy on birth outcomes. This hypothesis will be tested using the outcome of a trial of labor (achieved VBAC yes/no) in a cohort of women who are patients in a group practice with high rates of trial of labor. For ethical reasons, it is not possible to

randomize women into experimental and control groups. A retrospective case control design seeks to identify relationships among variables (Polit & Beck, 2012). Thus, the design of this study will be a retrospective case control design to determine the relationship between GWG and VBAC. Women with excessive weight gain will be compared to women with normal weight gain. Appropriateness of GWG will be determined in context of the revised IOM guidelines (Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009). Appropriateness of weight gain in the second and third trimesters will be analyzed, as well as weight gain overall.

Sample

This study will include a sample drawn from preexisting data from KPOC Obstetrics and Gynecology Nurse-Midwifery service that assists approximately 300-400 women a month in their delivery at two Kaiser Permanente hospitals in southern California. The target population is women who attempted a trial of labor between January 2009 and December 2013. The inclusion criteria are: spontaneous labor, history of only one low transverse cesarean delivery and no vaginal delivery, singleton gestation, and no uncontrolled co-morbidities (e.g., diabetes, hypertension, thyroid disorder, or seizure disorder). Women who do not fit these criteria will be excluded due to the likelihood of higher morbidity and mortality or lower vaginal birth after cesarean rates related to their uncontrolled co-morbidity. These criteria will be applied to control extraneous variables so that they do not become confounding variables when analyzing data to discover the relationship between weight gain in pregnancy and vaginal birth after cesarean (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, 2010; Guise et al., 2010).

Measures

Appendix C shows the study variables. The initial list of women will be gathered from the Nurse-Midwifery service log data that identifies those who chose a trial of labor and the outcomes of these deliveries. The electronic health records of these patients will be used to supplement data that is not available in the log. The following operational definitions developed for this study were used.

- Body Mass Index at onset of pregnancy: an index of body fat based on height and weight, calculated to determine the patient's obesity status. The calculation is the weight of the patient divided by the patient's height (kg/m^2). In this study, height measurement is collected at the first prenatal visit (Cunningham, Leveno, Bloom, Hauth, Rouse, & Spong, 2010). Weight at onset of pregnancy used to determine BMI will be gathered as discussed below.
- Pre-pregnancy BMI categories: underweight, normal weight, overweight, obese per IOM guidelines (Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009).
- Weight at onset of pregnancy: either patient weight at preconception visit (ideal), or recalled weight just prior to pregnancy documented during initial prenatal visits, or the first weight collected on the patient as long as the weight was collected during the first trimester of pregnancy (Cunningham et al., 2010; Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009).
- Second trimester weight gain: gestational gain during weeks 13-28 (Department of Health and Human Services, 2010). Second trimester gain will be the difference between the weight measured at the last first trimester visit and the weight at the earliest prenatal visit in the third trimester.

- Third trimester weight gain: gestational weeks 29 to the delivery (Department of Health and Human Services, 2010). Third trimester gain will be the difference between the weight measured at the last second trimester visit and the weight at the last prenatal visit prior to admission for labor.
- Excessive weight gain in pregnancy: weight gain during pregnancy that exceeds the most recent IOM guidelines from 2009 based on the woman's pre-pregnancy BMI (Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009). Excessive weight gain in second trimester - according to the 2009 revised IOM guidelines (Table 1); exceeding 1.3 lb per week for women who are underweight, exceeding an average of 1 lb per week for women who are of normal weight, exceeding an average of 0.7 lb per week for women who are overweight, exceeding an average of 0.6 lb per week for women who are obese (Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009).
- Excessive weight gain in third trimester: according to the 2009 revised IOM guidelines; exceeding 1.3 lb per week for women who are underweight, exceeding an average of 1 lb per week for women who are of normal weight, exceeding an average of 0.7 lb per week for women who are overweight, exceeding an average of 0.6 lb per week for women who are obese (Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009).
- Co-morbidity: any chronic or acute diseases or conditions that were determined to be significant enough to be listed on the patient's admission history and physical.
- Noted risk factor: any condition that increases medical risk that occurred or was present during pregnancy, labor, or delivery, and that is listed in the

medical record by the delivering provider.

- Anemia: hemoglobin of 11.0 g/dl or less upon admission for labor (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2011).
- Post term: gestation of 42 weeks 0 days and beyond (ACOG, 2013).
- Insufficient prenatal care: two or greater prenatal visits not attended, or entry to care after a gestation in which a woman would have regularly already attended two prenatal visits.
- Macrosomia: infant weight of 4000g or more at delivery (Boulet, Alexander, Salihu, & Pass, 2003).
- Advanced maternal age: age 35 or older upon admission for labor (ACOG, 2012).

Data Collection

The initial patient list will be gathered from the Kaiser Permanente Orange County (KPOC) Nurse-Midwifery service logbook. Each patient will be assigned a unique patient study number so as to de-identify data. This master list will be saved on the KPOC Anaheim Medical Center locked Nurse-Midwifery call room computer, under the primary investigator's user profile protected by a password only known to the primary investigator and locked at all times when not in use. A data collection tool was created in an interactive Portable Document Format (PDF) Adobe form (Appendix D); while a separate form will be used for each patient, the program auto populates data into statistical analysis software. Data will be obtained from the Nurse-Midwifery log book and the electronic medical record, as described above. The filled out de-identified data collection forms will be saved on the main investigator's password-protected laptop.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics will be used to describe the sample and pregnancy characteristics. The relationship between the seven patterns of GWG (Figure 2) and success of a trial of labor (VBAC achieved or not) will be determined using chi-squared analysis; a significance level of .05 will be used for this analysis. The hypothesis that there is a relationship between excessive weight gain in pregnancy and VBAC will be tested using logistic regression. Initial bivariate relationships (*t*-tests, chi squared) will be tested for logistic model inclusion between VBAC (yes/no) and second trimester weight gain appropriateness, third trimester weight gain appropriateness, overall GWG appropriateness, and demographic variables. Hierarchical logistic regressions will be run: pre-existing maternal variables, followed by pregnancy-related variables, followed by weight-related variables. Only related variables ($p < .10$) will be used as predictors.

Ethical Considerations

Data will not be collected until approvals have been received from the Kaiser Permanente Southern California and California State University, Fullerton Institutional Review Boards.

RESULTS

Sample Description Mock Write Up

Descriptive statistics will be used to describe the sample (Tables 2 and 3). The sample will be discussed in terms of age, race/ethnicity, reasons for the primary cesarean delivery, pre-pregnancy BMI categories, GWG, and any preexisting co-morbidities or risk factors. Pregnancy-related characteristics of the sample will also be reported including average GWG and weight gain for second and third trimester, length of gestation, and infant weight at birth, as well as the frequency and percentage of the sample with each listed pregnancy, labor, and delivery related co-morbidity or risk factor.

Patterns of Weight Gain Mock Write Up

Women will be categorized as to patterns of weight gain based upon the categories in Table 4. Appropriateness of weight gain by trimester and overall will be determined by BMI-assigned guideline recommendations (Rasmussen & Yaktine, 2009).

The most common weight gain patterns will be discussed, as well as the least common category of weight gain pattern.

Table 2

Demographic Characteristics of Sample

Characteristic	<i>n</i>	%
Reason for primary cesarean delivery		
Indicated repeat cesarean		
Failure to progress		
Fetal intolerance to labor		
Other		
Race/ethnicity (per patient identification)		
Hispanic		
Caucasian		
African American		
Asian (Southeast)		
Filipino		
Pacific Islander		
Indian (Asian)		
Middle Eastern		
Other		
Pre-pregnancy BMI		
Underweight		
Normal		
Overweight		
Obese		
Comorbidity/condition/risk factor during pregnancy, labor, delivery		
Drug/alcohol use in pregnancy		
Herpes simplex virus		
Diet-controlled A1 gestational diabetes		
Elevated 1 hour glucola, negative 3 hours glucose tolerance test		
Essential/chronic hypertension (controlled)		
Gestational hypertension (controlled)		
Hypothyroid condition (controlled/euthyroid)		
Low pregnancy associated plasma protein A		
Group beta streptococcus carrier		
Anemia		
Low lying placenta		
Intrauterine growth restriction/small for gestational age		
Antenatal testing during pregnancy		
Greater than 40 weeks 0 days gestation upon admission		
Post term		
Insufficient prenatal care		
Chorioamnionitis		
Abnormal fetal heart rate tracings (per log book)		
Macrosomia		
Advanced maternal age		
Other		
Intrapartum conditions/risk factors		
Intrapartum augmentation		
Intrapartum antibiotics		
Use of tocolytic during labor		
Prolonged second stage of labor (per log book)		
Shoulder dystocia		
Successful VBAC		

Note. *N* = x.

Table 3

Sample Characteristics

Characteristic	Mean	SD
Maternal age at delivery (years)		
Maternal age at primary cesarean delivery (years)		
Pre-pregnancy maternal body mass index (BMI)		
Overall gestational weight gain (lb)		
Second trimester gestation weight gain (lb)		
Third trimester gestational weight gain (lb)		
Gestational age of baby (days)		
Infant weight (g)		

Note. $N = x$.

Table 4

Relationship of Gestational Weight Gain Patterns and VBAC

Weight gain pattern during pregnancy	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i> (%) with VBAC	χ^2 <i>p</i> -value
1. 2 nd trimester OK/ 3 rd trimester OK/ overall OK				
2. 2 nd trimester OK/ 3 rd trimester +/- overall OK				
3. 2 nd trimester OK/ 3 rd trimester +/- overall +				
4. 2 nd trimester +/- 3 rd trimester +/- overall OK				
5. 2 nd trimester +/- 3 rd trimester OK/ overall OK				
6. 2 nd trimester +/- 3 rd trimester +/- overall OK				
7. 2 nd trimester +/- 3 rd trimester +/- overall +				
		100		

Note. $N = x$. VBAC = vaginal birth after cesarean; OK = Appropriate; + = Excessive.

* $p < .05$.

Determining Predictors of VBAC Mock Write Up

In order to minimize the number of variables in the logistic regression, bivariate relations will be determined with those of interest. Tables 5 and 6 show mock results from these analyses. Maternal characteristics significantly related to VBAC will be discussed in terms of their relationships. Pregnancy characteristics found to be significantly related will be discussed. Intrapartum conditions significantly related to VBAC will also be discussed. Variables with significant associations to VBAC will be entered into a binary hierarchical logistic regression with grouped variables in the following order: maternal demographics, pregnancy, intrapartum conditions.

Table 5

Mean Values for Predictors as a Function of VBAC

Characteristic	VBAC (n = ?)	No VBAC (n = ?)	t-test p- value
Maternal age at delivery (years)			
Maternal age at primary cesarean delivery (years)			
Pre-pregnancy maternal body mass index (BMI)			
Overall gestational weight gain (lb)			
Second trimester gestational weight gain (lb)			
Third trimester gestational weight gain (lb)			
Gestational age of baby (days)			
Infant weight (g)			

Note. N = x. t-test used.

*p < .05.

Table 6

Frequencies for Non-Continuous Variables and Achieving VBAC

Variable	VBAC (n = ?)	No VBAC (n = ?)	χ^2 p- value
Drug/alcohol use in pregnancy			
Herpes simplex virus			
Diet controlled A1 gestational diabetes			
Elevated 1 hour glucola, negative 3 hour glucose tolerance test			
Essential/chronic hypertension (controlled)			
Gestational hypertension (controlled)			
Hypothyroidism condition (controlled/euthyroid)			
Low pregnancy associated plasma protein A			
Group beta streptococcus carrier			
Anemia			
Low lying placenta			
Intrauterine growth restriction/small for gestational age			
Antenatal testing during pregnancy			
Greater than 40 weeks 0 days gestation upon admission for labor			
Post term			
Insufficient prenatal care			
Chorioamnionitis			
Abnormal fetal heart rate tracing (per log book)			
Macrosomia			
Advanced maternal age			
Intrapartum augmentation			
Intrapartum antibiotics given			
Use of tocolytic during labor			
Prolonged second stage of labor			
Shoulder dystocia			

Note. N = . Chi-square test used.

*p < .05.

A binary logistic regression will be run with x independent variables. Predictors will be discussed and illustrated in Table 7. The x-variable model will be discussed in terms of whether it led to a good fit with the data (non-significant Hosmer and Lemeshow test). The ability of the model to predict "x%" of the variance in VBAC will be discussed, and case classification of VBAC increase will be illustrated. As seen in Table 7, variables that contributed independently to the overall model will be explained. Odds ratios found from variables will also be described.

Conclusion

Significant findings will be briefly highlighted, as well as what the analysis illustrated. It will be discussed whether these findings were predicted, and any other interesting findings.

Table 7

Summary of Logistic Regression Analysis Predicting VBAC

Variable	Beta	SE	Odds ratio [95% CI]	Wald statistic
Maternal age at delivery (years)				
Maternal age at primary cesarean section (years)				
Pre-pregnancy maternal body mass index (BMI)				
Weight gain during pregnancy (lb)				
Gestational age of baby (days)				
Infant weight (g)				
Drug/alcohol use in pregnancy				
Herpes simplex virus				
Diet controlled A1 gestational diabetes				
Elevated 1 hour glucola, negative 3 hour glucose tolerance test				
Essential/chronic hypertension (controlled)				
Gestational hypertension (controlled)				
Hypothyroid condition (controlled/euthyroid)				
Low pregnancy associated plasma protein A				
Group beta streptococcus carrier				
Anemia				
Low lying placenta				
Intrauterine growth restriction/small for gestational age				
Antenatal testing during pregnancy				
Greater than 40 weeks 0 days gestation upon admission				
Post term				
Insufficient prenatal care				
Chorioamnionitis				
Abnormal fetal heart rate tracing (per log book)				
Macrosomia				
Advanced maternal age				
Intrapartum augmentation				
Use of tocolytic during labor				
Prolonged second stage of labor				
Shoulder dystocia at delivery				
Second trimester GWG (total in pounds)				
Third trimester GWG (total in pounds)				

Note. $N = x$. CI = confidence interval. $X^2(df) = \dots, p = \dots$; Nagelkerke $R^2 = \dots\%$.

* $p < .05$. GWG = gestational weight gain.

DISCUSSION

Study findings will address a critical gap in research: that of factors contributing to VBAC (NIH, 2010). The aims of this study are to investigate the relationship of gestational weight gain overall and more specifically patterns of gestational weight gain, to the achievement of VBAC in a low- to moderate risk population of women who are managed by nurse-midwives.

In addition, other variables that may influence the likelihood of VBAC were studied. Several studies have examined the effects of obesity, excessive weight gain according to pre-2009 guidelines, demographics, and co-morbidities on the route of delivery. Various factors have surfaced that are inversely related to a spontaneous vaginal delivery with or without a history of primary cesarean delivery. Increasing maternal age, increasing BMI, increasing gestational age, and increasing infant weight have all been inversely related to a vaginal route of delivery; in other words, these factors predict that a trial of labor would be less likely to result in a vaginal delivery for those who have had a prior cesarean. Demographic factors such as race and ethnicity, and co-morbidities such as hypertension, diabetes, asthma, seizures, and cardiac, renal, and thyroid disease are inversely related to spontaneous vaginal delivery. Thus far, no screening tool has proven sufficient as a predictor of VBAC; however, spontaneous labor, having a *favorable* cervix, appropriate BMI according to pre-2009 guidelines, and infant weight less than 4000g have been linked to increasing success (NIH, 2010).

Knowledge of these predictors and other implications of excessive GWG led to the IOM's revised guidelines on weight gain during pregnancy. Subsequently, the NIH consensus statement on vaginal birth after cesarean was issued, and a month later ACOG

concluded in their Practice Bulletin Number 115 (ACOG, 2010; NIH 2010). With the availability of quality research and professional organizations supporting VBAC, an increasing number of women are seeking trial of labor. Within the NIH (2010) statement, further research was recommended. The concluding recommendation of 10 critical gaps in research was a call for research focusing on factors that contribute to VBAC, as determined by characterizing risk factors of an unsuccessful trial of labor.

Weight gain patterns in low-risk and moderate-risk women and their relationship to VBAC are important to the obstetric community. With current evidence in mind, it is hypothesized that excessive weight gain in pregnancy in all categories according to the 2009 guidelines will be related to decreased success of a trial of labor. Research available on this topic is based upon pre-2009 revised gestational weight gain guidelines, however supports this hypothesis. Most studies conclude that there is a significant relationship between obesity and/or excessive weight gain resulting in a high BMI by the end of the pregnancy (Bujold et al., 2006; Chauhan et al., 2001; Durnwald et al., 2004; Goodall et al., 2004; Hibbard et al., 2006; NIH, 2010). Juhasz et al. (2005) found that obesity (as defined as greater than 29.0 kg/m²) or gaining over 40 pounds in pregnancy were both significant risk factors for a failed trial of labor.

Co-morbidities and demographics will also be explored to offer a comparative analysis to weight gain in pregnancy. Previous research has demonstrated that key demographic variables are related to VBAC rates, and it is hypothesized this may be illustrated in this study as well. Race and ethnicity, specifically Hispanic or African American, and increasing maternal age are related to decreased rates of VBAC (NIH, 2011). Maternal disease, gestation longer than 40 weeks, augmentation of labor, infant

weight of 4000 grams or more, and presence of an unfavorable cervix are also linked to decreased VBAC rates (NIH, 2010).

A clinically important hypothesis to be investigated is the NIH (2010) Critical Gap Number 10 recommendation seeking to characterize factors that increase risk for trial of labor failure. The finding by Chmitorz et al. (2012) that excessive second trimester weight gain strongly predicts excessive third trimester gain in a sample of women who were not recipients of intervention outside routine care, entails significant implications for obstetrical providers. This may imply that without ancillary education and support, women with excessive mid-pregnancy weight gain are at greater risk for excessive overall gain, and may possibly benefit from targeted guidance. Durie, Thornburg, and Glantz (2011) found that when the sum of second and third trimester weight gain was excessive this increased risk for cesarean delivery, which posits when overall weight gain (operationalized as the sum of second and third trimester gain) is appropriate, risk of cesarean delivery will be lower. Unfortunately the authors did not report on the number of women in their sample who gained excessively in the second trimester then slowed in the third trimester, to equal a sum of overall second and third trimester appropriate weight gain. However, this look at the more linear rate of weight gain in the second and third trimesters (as compared to including the non-linear rate of first trimester weight gain) is promising support to the hypothesis that controlled weight gain in the third trimester after excessive in the second may be related to higher rates of VBAC.

With the knowledge that excessive second trimester weight gain strongly predicts excessive third trimester gain in the absence of supplementary intervention, obstetric

clinicians are able to target women at the end of the second trimester who may yet still be able to increase their likelihood of vaginal delivery. Better understanding of the association between improved weight gain in the third trimester after excessive weight gain in the second trimester in low-risk and moderate-risk women should offer important implications to clinicians. This suggests an effective education tool and area of further research in supporting VBAC.

Study aims are to characterize factors associated with VBAC success. These findings may assist in developing targeted education, treatment, and strategies to provide a safe environment for these women prior to, and during pregnancy. They may also provide research-based evidence for women's health clinicians (nurse-midwives, nurse-practitioners, and physicians) that will assist women to make informed decisions regarding route of delivery after a primary cesarean.

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APPENDIX A

TABLE OF EVIDENCE 1

Table of Evidence: Trial of Labor after Cesarean, Vaginal Birth after Cesarean, High Pre-pregnancy Body Mass Index and Gestational Weight Gain

Study	N/n obese attempt TOLAC	VBAC rate underweight-normal/ overweight-obese	Obesity definition	Key Findings/Conclusions	Limitations
Hibbard et al., 2006	14,142/ 1,638	78-85%/ 61-70%	Overweight: BMI \geq 30.0-39.9 kg/m ² , Obese: BMI \geq 40.0 kg/m ²	Morbidly obese women 40% failure rate vs. 15% in normal weight women	Uncertain of bias in counsel to women regarding TOLAC vs. ERCD
Durnwald, Ehrenberg, & Mercer, 2004	510/ 163	65.5-84.7%/ 54.6%	BMI \geq 30 kg/m ²	Reduction in success rate began at \geq 30 BMI kg/m ² Obese women up to 44% failure rate vs. up to 29% in normal weight women	Lacks adequate power, post hoc power analysis showed a need for n = 848 Uncertain of bias in counsel to women regarding TOLAC vs. ERCD Overweight vs. obese?
Goodall, Ahn, Chapa, & Hibbard, 2004	725/ 248	80-86%/ 70-72%	Overweight: BMI \geq 30.0-39.9 kg/m ² , Obese: BMI \geq 40.0 kg/m ²	Overweight/obese women 27-30% failure rate vs. 14-20% in low to normal weight women	Small number of patients Power analysis not done
Juhasz, Gynamfi, Gynamfi, Tocce, & Stone, 2005	1213/ 201	80-83%/ 69% Women gaining > 40lbs illustrated a rate of 68% VBAC rate	Obese: > 29.0 kg/m ² , or over 40 lbs GWG	Gaining > 40 lbs 40% less chance VBAC than gaining < 40 lbs Obese women 32% failure rate vs. 17-20% in normal weight women	Did not discuss bias in counsel to women regarding TOLAC vs. ERCD Did not delineate between overweight and obese
Chauhan et al, 2001	436 (not studied but VBAC rate recorded)/	Only gave average rate for all TOLAC women = 68%/ 13%	Morbidly obese: BMI \geq 40.0 kg/m ² Mean BMI 57.2 +/-	Morbidly obese women high morbidity and failure rates with TOLAC	Did not study overweight women Small sample size

Study	N/n obese attempt TOLAC	VBAC rate underweight-normal/ overweight-obese	Obesity definition	Key Findings/Conclusions	Limitations
	30		9.2		Included counseling, consent processes
Bujold, Hammoud, Schild, Krapp, & Baumann, 2005	6718/ 2607	74-78%/ 52-69%	Overweight 1: BMI 30.0-34.9 kg/m ² , Overweight 2: BMI 34.9-39.9 kg/m ² Obese: BMI ≥ 40.0 kg/m ²	↑BMI independent factor for failed TOLAC ERCD not associated with better outcomes (patient, neonate)	Did not adjust for reason of prior cesarean delivery and current gestational diabetes (data unavailable). Did not discuss counseling or consent process
Carroll, Magann, Chauhan, Klauser, & Morrison, 2003	91/ 58	82%/ 13-57%	Group 1: < 200 lb, Group 2: 200-300 lb, Group 3: > 300 lb	Women 200-300 lb showed VBAC rate >50% and considered still appropriate to counsel on attempting TOLAC. Women > 300 lb should be counseled for ERCD	Small sample size Did not discuss counsel and consent process
Homee, Kurinczuk, Spark, Brocklehurst, & Knight, 2010	417/ 417	69%	All participants: BMI ≥ 50.0 kg/m ²	Main outcome goals - look at complications for mother and neonate with VBAC vs. ERCD Results of successful VBAC vs. failed TOLAC to achieve outcome goals	Did not discuss counsel and consent process Data retrieved from national cohort database that has been known to miss cases related to data entry error
Durie, Thornburgm & Glantz, 2011	24% out of 73,977	N/A Not specific to TOLAC	2009 IOM guidelines	Excessive GWG in 2 nd & 3 rd trimester = increased risk for cesarean delivery.	Not specific to TOLAC. Did not report 2nd&3rd GWG separately
Krukowski, Bursac, McGehee, & West, 2013	n = 4619 categories not reported however number of	N/A Not specific to TOLAC	2009 IOM guidelines	Overweight or obese pre-pregnancy was illustrated as the strongest predictor of excessive gestational weight gain	Not specific to TOLAC Participants African American and Caucasian, applicability to other ethnicities is unknown

Study	<i>N/n</i> obese attempt TOLAC	VBAC rate underweight-normal/ overweight-obese	Obesity definition	Key Findings/Conclusions	Limitations
	women who gained appropriate vs excessive reported			Excessive gestational weight gain was illustrated as a risk Potentially modifiable factor for pregnancy complications such as gestational diabetes, preeclampsia, caesarean delivery	
Langford, Joshu, Chang, Myles, & Leet, 2011	<i>n</i> = 34143, all participants were overweight by pre-2009 guidelines	N/A not specific to TOLAC	Pre-2009 IOM guidelines	Increasing GWG (> 25lb) = increased cesarean delivery in women who are overweight	Pre-2009 IOM guidelines Observational study Baseline BMI collected from maternal recall Not specific to TOLAC
Magann et al., 2011	<i>n</i> = 4286, of these 26% were obese	N/A not specific to TOLAC	Pre-2009 guidelines	28 lb gain by 28 wks in women with BMI of 25-32 = higher risk for cesarean delivery	Retrospective study All cohorts were from a tertiary center, may not be applicable to other environments Not specific to TOLAC
Margerison-Zilko, Rehkopf, & Abrams, 2010	<i>n</i> = 4496	N/A not specific to TOLAC	Pre-2009 guidelines	Excessive weight gain (according to pre-2009 guidelines) is associated with primary cesarean delivery	Did not report 2nd vs 3rd trimester weight gain Not specific to TOLAC Retrospective

Note. BMI = body mass index; ERCDC = elective repeat cesarean delivery; GWG = gestational weight gain; TOLAC = trial of labor after cesarean; VBAC = vaginal birth after cesarean.

APPENDIX B

TABLE OF EVIDENCE 2

Table of Evidence Exclusion Criteria for Trial of Labor after Cesarean Section

Study	N	Objective	Exclusion Criteria	Methods	Findings, Limitations, Comments
Spontaneous versus induced labor after a previous cesarean delivery (Delaney & Young, 2003).	3746, 2943 spontaneous labors, 803 induction of labors	To compare outcomes and complications amongst spontaneous labor versus induction of labor in women with history of one low transverse cesarean delivery scar	Multiple gestation, placenta previa, previous uterine surgery other than primary cesarean delivery, herpes simplex outbreak at time of delivery, malpresentation, more than one cesarean delivery history	-Data gathered through retrospective record review. - χ^2 test and Fisher's test, $P < .05$. Logistic regression carried out to control for covariate	-Greater uterine rupture rates in women with history of cesarean delivery who underwent induction of labor (0.7%) vs. women who did not (0.3%) -Other complications in induction group similar to women who undergo induction of labor who have not had a previous cesarean delivery (postpartum hemorrhage, necessity of cesarean delivery, infant admission to NICU without long-term complication) -Induction of labor not advised in women with prior history cesarean delivery -Limitations: retrospective.
Uterine rupture associated with misoprostol labor induction in women with previous cesarean delivery (Aslan, Unlu, Agar, & Ceylan, 2002)	97	To review data on women who undergo induction of labor with misoprostol and who have history of one prior cesarean delivery	Bishop score <6, intrauterine fetal demise prior to admission, unexplained bleeding, previous cesarean delivery with classical incision, and malpresentation.	-Vaginal then oral administration of 50 mcg then 100 mcg misoprostol, then oxytocin augmentation as needed -Patients with/without scaring compared: mode of delivery, complications, evidence of uterine rupture - χ^2 test and Fisher's test, $P < .05$., 95% CI -Retrospective study	-Patients with history of cesarean delivery who were induced with misoprostol showed significantly greater rate of uterine rupture vs. women without -Uterine rupture rate in previous cesarean delivery patients 9.7% (vs. < 1% in women with previous cesarean delivery who are not induced) -Limitations: small sample size, not randomized control trial

Study	N	Objective	Exclusion Criteria	Methods	Findings, Limitations, Comments
Vaginal birth after two caesarean sections (VBAC-2)- A systematic review with meta-analysis of success rate and adverse outcomes of VBAC-2 versus VBAC-1 and repeat (third) caesarean sections (Tahseen, & Griffiths, 2009)	17 studies (5666 patients total undergoing labor) of the original 273 were included	Evaluate success and complications associated with trial of labor after two cesarean deliveries through systematic review	Case reports and studies that showed poor methodology	-Meta-analysis performed by methods suggested by the MOOSE group -Data collected by two authors who worked independently of each other, then resolved any differences in collection through discussion. -Retrospective review study	-Success rate of vaginal delivery 45%-89%, not much difference between groups. -Meta-analysis: group without prior vaginal delivery showed greater need for cesarean delivery, but only by about 5% -Women with history of 2 VBACs greater risk for uterine rupture (1.59% vs. 0.72%) -Need for blood transfusion and infection lower in women with a history ≤ 1 previous cesarean section -Small increase in risk; enough to recommend TOLAC only if woman has a history of only one cesarean delivery -Limitations: time span over 2 decades, not randomized control trials
More than one previous cesarean delivery: A 5-year experience with 435 patients (Asakura, & Myers, 1995)	435 with > 1 previous cesarean section, 1206 with 1 previous cesarean section	-To compare outcomes of women with a history of one vaginal delivery to women with a history of two cesarean deliveries as to their delivery route and evidence of complications	-Woman's refusal to undergo trial of labor, desire for sterilization, or other medical indications (not listed)	- χ^2 test and Fisher's test, $P < .05$, 95% CI. -Convenience sample study	-Adverse outcomes other than wound separation not \uparrow with women > 1 cesarean deliveries -Wound separation \uparrow women with >1 cesarean delivery vs. women with only 1, except results not statistically significant (2.5% vs 1.1%) -Women with one prior cesarean delivery more likely to deliver vaginally rather than have repeat cesarean delivery ($P < .05$) -Vaginal delivery may be appropriate in the right conditions; slight increased risk for uterine rupture (not statistically significant), lower chance for vaginal delivery making it less than optimal to recommend.

Study	N	Objective	Exclusion Criteria	Methods	Findings, Limitations, Comments
Intrapartum uterine rupture and dehiscence in patients with prior lower uterine segment vertical and transverse incisions (Shipp et al., 1999)	2912 women with a low transverse scar, and 377 women with a low vertical scar	To compare outcomes of women who undergo a trial of labor after cesarean delivery with a vertical incision compared to women with a low transverse incision	Women whose scar extended past lower uterine segment into corpus of uterus excluded due to known increase risk	-Records reviewed extending a 12 year period of women who fit the inclusion criteria. - χ^2 test and Fisher's test, $P < .05$ -Logistic regression analysis compare confounding factors. -Retrospective study	-Limitations: unknown what "medical indications" used for exclusion -Outcomes of scar separation similar, 1.3% in low transverse vs. 1.0% low vertical group - Women with low vertical scar do not contribute to increase risk as previously seen in women with "classical" vertical incisions in uterine corpus; results similar to low transverse uterine scar TOLAC results
A 10-year population-based study of uterine rupture (Keiser & Baskett, 2002)	39 cases of rupture out of 114,933 deliveries. 36 women had history of previous cesarean section, 33 low transverse, 2 classic, 1 low vertical incision	To compare mortality and morbidity of women who had history of different uterine scars: low transverse, low vertical, or classical vertical incision into the corpus of the uterine body	Women with history of scar separation had charts reviewed further, women without scar separation excluded	- 10 year retrospective chart review from patient database -Retrospective study -- χ^2 test and Fisher's test, $P < .05$., 95% CI	-No maternal deaths -3 complete scar dehiscences (compared to only partial) in women with vertical uterine scars -2 fetal deaths in women with scar separation, one woman had a history of previous cesarean delivery -Short term infant complications -Limitations: data on classical incisions limited due to known danger of complications with future pregnancy, thus this type of incision is not commonly seen in a patients history

Note. NICU = neonatal intensive care unit; TOLAC = trial of labor after cesarean; VBAC = vaginal birth after cesarean.

APPENDIX C

LIST OF VARIABLES

Variable Table

Data	Obtained	Operational definition
Age at primary cesarean and then delivery/or repeat cesarean	EMR	Per documented date
Reason for primary cesarean	Logbook	Patient recall, transferred medical records, or as documented in the electronic medical record
Baseline weight in pounds during preconception visit or during first trimester (initial weight)	EMR	Patient weight at preconception visit (ideal) or recalled weight just prior to pregnancy documented during
Height in inches	EMR	As recorded in the electronic medical record at the first prenatal visit
Body mass index category per Institute of Medicine (2009) guidelines	Category assignment	Under (<18.5 kg/m ²) Normal (18.5-24.9 kg/ m ²) Overweight (25.0-29.9 kg/ m ²) Obese (≥30.0 kg/ m ²)
Race or ethnicity	Logbook	As recorded in log book
Co Morbidities (not to include uncontrolled diabetes, uncontrolled hypertension, thyroid disease, or seizure disorder)	Logbook/ EMR	As listed in admission history and physical for labor, or discharge summary, either no medical problems or history of diet controlled gestational diabetes, controlled gestational or essential hypertension, euthyroid hypothyroidism on supplementation, low lying placenta, history of drug or alcohol use during pregnancy, insufficient prenatal care, group beta streptococcus carrier, abnormal one hour glucola in pregnancy with a negative 3-hr glucose tolerance test (< 2 elevations), anemia, low pregnancy associated plasma protein A, post-dates, post-term, attended antenatal testing for any reason, intrauterine growth restriction/small for gestational age
Gestation at time of delivery	Logbook	As recorded in log book
Labor and delivery variables	Log book/ EMR	Length of labor Yes/No answers: occurrence of shoulder dystocia, prolonged second stage of labor, intrapartum augmentation, diagnosis
Weight gain during pregnancy	EMR	Last documented weight in pounds minus baseline pregnancy weight in pounds
Stayed within IOM guidelines of gestational weight gain?	Calculation	Yes/no
Delivery outcome – VBAC or not?	Logbook	Yes/no
If delivery outcome was not VBAC, reason for cesarean delivery?	Logbook	Yes/no for each: fetal intolerance of labor, arrest of labor, comorbidity, other
Age at delivery	Logbook	Per documentation

Note. EMR = electronic medical record; VBAC = vaginal birth after.

APPENDIX D

DATA COLLECTION SHEET

Unique Patient Study Number

Data Collection Sheet

Demographics-History-Comorbidities & Risk Factors Data

Variable	Data	Reason for <i>primary</i> cesarean		
Age at primary cesarean		Indicated Repeat Cesarean	Failure to Progress/ labor arrest	Fetal Intolerance of Labor
Baseline weight, pounds				
Last pregnancy weight in pounds				
Height in inches				

(not related to
other columns)

Race or ethnicity

Hispanic	Caucasian	Asian (Southeast)
African American	Filipino	Pacific Islander
Indian (Asian)	Middle Eastern	Other

Comorbidities/conditions/risk factors present during pregnancy/labor/delivery

Drug/alcohol use in pregnancy	Herpes simplex virus	Diet-controlled A1 gestational diabetes
Elevated 1 hour glucola, negative 3 hour tolerance test	Essential hypertension/chronic hypertension (controlled)	Gestational hypertension (controlled)
Hypothyroid condition (controlled/euthyroid)	Low pregnancy associated plasma protein A	Group beta streptococcus carrier
Anemia	Low lying placenta	Growth restriction/ small for gestational age
Antenatal testing during pregnancy	Post dates	Post term
Insufficient prenatal care	Chorioamnionitis	Abnormal fetal heart rate tracings (per logbook)
Macrosomia	Advanced maternal age	Other

Intrapartum Data

Variable	Data	Weeks	Days
Infant birth weight in grams		Gestation at delivery	
Age at delivery			

Variable	Select if Yes
Intrapartum augmentation?	
Intrapartum antibiotics given?	
Use of tocolytic during labor?	
Prolonged 2nd stage of labor?	
Shoulder dystocia at delivery?	
Vaginal birth after cesarean?	

Reason for *repeat* cesarean delivery

Indicated repeat cesarean	Failure to progress/ labor arrest	Fetal intolerance of labor
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(not related to
other columns)